

Communication and Dissemination Plan, materials and website

Deliverable 9.1

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Lead Partner: Greenovate! Europe
Contributor(s): CSCP

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Dissemination and awareness activities are a core part of the SCALIBUR project and will maximise the opportunities for SCALIBUR results to be used and exploited at European level after the project's end.

All partners are required by the Grant and Consortium Agreements to disseminate their generated results and all are requested to contribute to communication and awareness raising activities, by proactively looking for dissemination opportunities and making their own communication channels available, in order to reach the European-wide audience.

This report includes all the communication & dissemination activities carried out in the first 24 months of the project.

A plan of action for the second half of the project is also included, including information on target audiences, a list of results, planned dissemination and communication activities.

To assess the effectiveness of the communication and dissemination actions progress is reported towards a set of Key Performance Indicators which were defined at the start of the project.

This document should be considered as a reference for project partners when conducting communication and dissemination activities.

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